

OPTIMISATION OF FORMING PROCESS FOR HIGHLY DRAPEABLE FABRICS

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ABSTRACT

A genetic algorithm is coupled with a finite element model to optimise the arrangement of constraints for a composite press-forming problem. A series of springs are used to locally apply in-plane tension through clamps to the fibre preform to control material draw-in. The optimisation procedure seeks to minimise local in-plane shear angles by determining the optimum location and size of constraining clamps, and the stiffness of connected springs. Results are presented for a double-dome geometry, which are compared against data from the literature using alternative means to apply constraints. Controlling material draw-in using in-plane constraints around the blank perimeter is an effective way of homogenising the shear angle distribution and minimising the maximum shear angle. However, an alternative set-up with a segmented blank holder has the potential to produce fewer wrinkles in the fabric due to lower peak compressive strains along the fibre directions.

1 INTRODUCTION

The preparation and handling of textile preforms is labour-intensive and difficult to automate for composite components with complex geometry. Historically, fabric forming processes have been developed based on knowledge gained from metal forming. Blank holders are typically used to apply a normal pressure to the fabric blank to control material draw-in through in-plane friction, as shown in Fig. 1(a) [1-5]. Unlike metals however, the formability of fabrics is controlled mainly by fibre reorientation, i.e. fabric shear, rather than plastic flow. Moderate fibre rotation and slip are required to allow fabric to be formed, which are affected by blank holding forces. The blank holding force is the most significant process parameter affecting formability [3, 6-9]. Results from finite element simulations have shown that forming behaviour is very sensitive to the distribution of blank holding force [3], with segmented blank holders used in a number of studies [6, 9, 10] to apply variable forces around the perimeter of the die. Long et al. [10] successfully reduced the wrinkling strain by 30-50 % by manually optimising blank-holding forces for each blank-holder segment. Skordos et al. [11] used a genetic algorithm to optimise the blank-holding force distribution for a segmented blank holder, minimising wrinkling by avoiding localised buckling of the tows.

It is difficult to handle dry textile without inducing in-plane distortion, which can cause problems when loading material into the forming tool. One possible solution is to constrain the edges of the blank around the perimeter using spring-loaded clamps, as shown in Fig. 1(b). These clamps are connected to a rigid outer frame and remain outside of the punch/die area during forming. They also apply in-plane tension to the fabric to control material draw-in, eliminating the need for a blank holder [12-14]. This arrangement was originally developed for processing unconsolidated thermoplastic fabrics, facilitating preheating of the sheets, but more recently has been adopted by the automotive industry for preforming non-crimp fabrics. Finite element models have been developed to investigate the feasibility of using edge clamps to control material draw-in of thermoplastic sheets [12-14]

This study seeks to optimise the spring-loaded clamping arrangement, which is used to apply in-plane tension to the fabric blank to control material draw-in. A genetic algorithm (GA) is coupled with an explicit finite element model to minimise local shear angles and to reduce wrinkling. Results from this optimisation study are compared to data from the literature for the same component, using a

segmented blank holder to apply in-plane friction via a normal force. The quality of the formed component is compared for the two blank constraining methods.

2 OPTIMISATION METHODOLOGY

The procedure to optimise the spring-loaded clamping arrangement shown in Fig. 1(b) is split into two stages; Step I: Clamping arrangement optimisation; Step II: Spring stiffness optimisation. The first step determines clamping positions resulting in reduced maximum global shear angle in the model. Compromises have to be made however, as it is not practical to constrain every position around the blank perimeter. The second step determines optimum spring stiffnesses for the derived clamp arrangement. Therefore, the obtained solution may not be the global optimum, but near-optimal.

Figure 1: Two scenarios to constrain preforms during fabric forming. (a) Segmented blank holder; (b) spring-loaded clamps.

2.1 Step I: Clamping arrangement optimisation

In the finite element model, each node around the perimeter of the blank is initially constrained to a rigid frame by an individual spring element with the same initial stiffness. When the node is unconstrained, the connected spring element is removed. A binary encoding method is applied to formulate each individual in-plane constraining pattern, where each bit in the code represents one potential constraint position and its value corresponds to an “unconstrained” or “constrained” status (0 or 1). A maximum value criterion (MAXVC) [15] has been adopted here as the fitness function to assess each individual constraining pattern. The objective is therefore to keep all local shear angles below the locking angle, by minimising the maximum shear angle. The maximum can be derived from the finite element approximation for the shear angle distribution.

To enable industrial implementation, the optimised patterns need to be simplified by grouping together neighbouring constraints to form consolidated clamps:

- Two adjacent positions are considered to be part of the same clamp, if their distance is smaller than a threshold value;

- Any isolated clamps smaller than a specific minimum clamp size are discarded;
- Clamps are removed or split if they generate excessive curvature around the perimeter of the blank or increase MAXVC.

The stiffness of each constraint is directly obtained by summing the stiffnesses of all parallel springs associated with each individual clamp. The negative impact can be alleviated to some extent by optimising the spring properties in Step II. Here, these practical considerations have been implemented manually, which is facilitated by the two-stage optimisation approach.

2.2 Step II: Spring stiffness optimisation

In-plane constraints are applied at the selected clusters of nodes identified in Step I. A subsequent optimisation step is performed using a GA to determine optimum stiffness values for each spring from a user-defined range. MAXVC is employed again as the fitness function to minimise the maximum shear angle in Step II. In this step, optimisation is aimed at finding a near-optimal solution to reduce the negative influence induced by manually refining the constrained positions.

2.3 Model settings and optimisation parameters

The constraints were optimized using Matlab combined with Abaqus/Explicit. The Matlab GA Toolbox was employed to manage the manipulation and evaluation of the optimisation process. The Abaqus/Explicit solver was invoked to run submitted jobs and then results were returned to Matlab for further GA fitness assessment.

Material parameters were consistent with values in the literature [5, 6, 15-17] for a balanced plain weave glass fibre/polypropylene commingled fabric. The value of Young's modulus was taken to be 35.4 GPa in each fibre direction, and the shear modulus was described by a polynomial:

$$G_{12} = (6.7135|\gamma_{12}|^4 - 9.8228|\gamma_{12}|^3 + 6.3822|\gamma_{12}|^2 - 1.5928|\gamma_{12}| + 0.1948) \text{ MPa} \quad (1)$$

where γ_{12} is the in-plane shear angle in radians.

A single 0°/90° ply with dimensions 470 mm × 270 mm at a thickness of 0.4 mm was modelled using quadrilateral membrane elements (M3D4R). Tooling surfaces were modelled as rigid bodies; Coulomb friction was adopted for both tooling-material and material-material contacts, with a coefficient of 0.2; displacement boundary conditions were applied to the punch.

Since all nodes along the edges were initially connected to springs in Step I, it was necessary to choose a relatively low starting stiffness from the available range to avoid over-constraining the blank. In this step, the constraint stiffness was set to 0.025 N/mm at each applied position. For Step II, the spring stiffnesses were selected to range from 0.025 N/mm to 0.500 N/mm.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Step I: Clamping arrangement optimisation

Several generations of clamping patterns have been selected to illustrate the optimisation evolution for Step I (Fig. 2), indicating the reduction in number of constraints and the evolution rate. Each generation represents a summary of 100 individual constraining patterns, where the bars represent constrained locations. An initial population of 100 patterns for the zeroth generation was generated randomly, which then evolved into subsequent generations according to the GA. In the figure, all bars are initially a shade of red, which indicates that all of the constraint positions are represented similarly across the 100 patterns. The shade of red changes as the constraining pattern evolves for each subsequent generation, where a darker red (tending towards black) represents a higher frequency for that constrained position. A lighter shade of red represents a lower frequency, where white indicates complete removal of the constraint. As the fitness function converges, all remaining bars appear black, which indicates that all 100 patterns for that generation are in agreement.

Figure 2: Optimisation evolution of constraining pattern in Step I; solid bars represent constrained positions in the respective generation; red scale indicates the frequencies of occurrence within the respective generation.

Figure 2 shows that some of the final constraint positions start to emerge as quickly as generation 7, with some bars already shown as black. By generation 14, some of the weaker bars are removed. By generation 35, there are very few red bars remaining, with the status of only 20 % of the clamping positions uncertain at this stage. The final clamping pattern is determined after generation 43, which is confirmed by comparing with the outcome from generation 51.

The influence of the clamping arrangement on the in-plane shear angles is shown in Fig. 3. The clamping arrangement in Fig. 3b is the optimum pattern from generation 43. This is compared against the fully constrained initial pattern assumed at the beginning of the optimisation process. The maximum shear angle decreases by 11.2° , from 48.2° for the fully constrained system (Fig. 3a) to 37.1° after all unconstrained springs have been removed (Fig. 3b). However, practical implementation of the optimum pattern in Fig. 3b is not feasible, since too many individual springs are required to obtain the blank boundary conditions. Therefore, it is necessary to compromise and combine neighbouring clamps and eliminate isolated ones (see Fig. 3c). The minimum threshold distance between clamps was chosen to be 25 mm (equivalent to the width of 5 finite elements), and the minimum clamp length was also assumed to be 25 mm. In addition, the spring located at the mid-point of the short edge (see Fig. 3b) was removed, as this could not be combined into a single clamp due to the region of high curvature generated by the springs either side. Consequently, only two clamps were required along each of the short edges to maintain the optimum draw-in. The individual constrained positions from Fig. 3b were combined and reduced to 14 clamps, as shown in Fig. 3c. The stiffness of each consolidated spring was directly obtained by summing the stiffness of all of the parallel springs belonging to each corresponding block.

Although the maximum shear angle increased by 3.4° in Fig. 3c compared with the result in Fig. 3b, this still yields an overall reduction in peak shear angle of 7.7° compared with the unoptimised case. In addition, the shear angle distribution in Fig. 3b indicates that wrinkling occurs along the long edges when constrained by individual springs, as there are local transitions in shear angle. However, these disappear in Fig. 3c when longer clamps are introduced along the edges. Constraining the blank using consolidated clamps homogenises the boundary constraints to eliminate undesirable wrinkling around the perimeter.

Figure 3: Step I – Clamping arrangement optimisation for a single 0°/90° ply.

Figure 4: Evolution of shear angle distribution from Step II of spring-loaded clamp optimisation.

3.2 Step II: Spring stiffness optimisation

The spring stiffnesses from the solution in Step I (Fig. 3c) form the starting point of the GA based optimisation in Step II. As shown in Fig. 4, the maximum shear angle is reduced to 37.2° by optimising the spring stiffnesses. This value differs by 0.1° from the ideal optimum (37.1°) in Step I (Fig. 3b). It indicates that the negative influence induced by manually combining the constrained positions into clamps is minimised by seeking an optimal combination of spring stiffnesses in Step II, whilst making the solution more practical.

The optimum combination of spring stiffnesses is illustrated schematically in Fig. 5. This figure allows a general strategy for spring placement to be derived: At zones of the component geometry with small curvature, springs with relatively low stiffness are attached to the blank through long clamps to provide near uni-axial tension. Zones with a high degree of curvature require multiple springs with stiffnesses adapted to suit the fibre orientation, which are attached through short localised clamps, allowing for multi-axial tension to be applied to the blank. In general, springs attached to the clamps along the long edges have a stiffness of 0.20 N/mm, and springs along the short edges are approximately 0.30 N/mm for the current geometry. These are of similar magnitude to those used by Harrison et al. [13], where fewer clamps were used, and the stiffer springs were placed on the long edges.

Figure 5: Schematic of locations and widths of clamps; spring stiffnesses are also indicated.

3.3 Comparison with constraint application through blank holders

Results from the two-stage spring/clamp optimisation have been compared against results from a segmented blank holder approach, for the same double hemisphere geometry. The geometry of the blank holder, which was taken from the International Forming Benchmark study [5, 6, 15, 16], is divided into six segments (Fig. 1a). The force applied on each segment has been established using the same GA optimisation method as described above, where the range of the blank holder force was selected to be from 0.01 kN to 1.00 kN.

As shown in Fig. 6, the maximum shear angle is reduced to 42.5° by optimising the forces applied to the blank holder segments. This is 4° smaller than the initial generation and is comparable to values reported in the literature [5, 6, 16]. The optimum solution in Fig. 6 for the segmented blank holder constraint can be directly compared to the optimum distribution in Fig. 4 for the spring-loaded clamp constraint. The spring-loaded clamps appear to be a more effective way of reducing local shear angle, with the maximum value (37.2°) more than 5° smaller than for the blank holder approach (42.5°). However, Fig. 4 indicates that there are more significant local transitions in shear angle for the spring-loaded clamps than for the blank holder, which may result in the onset of severe wrinkling.

Figure 6: Evolution of shear angle distribution from segmented blank holder force optimisation.

Figure 7 illustrates in-plane strains along the two principal fibre directions, where only negative strains are shown to indicate fabric compression, which may result in localised wrinkles. These results indicate that the shear angle distributions and wrinkling strain are not independent objectives, as previously seen in the literature [17]. Due to larger maximum shear strains for the case using spring-loaded clamps, (3.6 %), the wrinkling risk is higher than for the case using a segmented blank holder (2.2 %). This implies that using blank-holders applying a normal force to the fabric surface may help to control the occurrence of wrinkles, as they provide resistance to out-of-plane deformation of the blank whilst providing in-plane tension to control material draw-in.

Whilst smaller in-plane shear angles were achieved with the spring-loaded clamping arrangement, the segmented blank holder set-up can potentially be further improved through optimisation of shape and position of the segments to reduce the maximum shear angle.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A scenario has been introduced for controlling material draw-in during reinforcement forming processes, using a series of in-plane springs to locally apply tension to the preform, rather than using a blank holder to compress the preform out-of-plane and apply constraints through friction. A non-orthogonal constitutive relation has been defined for bi-axial materials with large deformation, based on a VFABRIC model in Abaqus/Explicit. The in-plane constraints around the edges were modelled using spring elements connected to a fully constrained rigid frame, providing axial forces to control material slippage into the cavity.

An optimisation methodology has been developed by combining an explicit FE model with a genetic algorithm to optimise constraints for fabric forming simulations. It has been utilised to optimise a clamp/spring arrangement to provide suitable in-plane tension to a fabric blank during forming. It has been implemented in two stages; Step I: Clamping arrangement optimisation; Step II: Spring stiffness optimisation. Process optimisation has been demonstrated using a double-dome geometry from the literature. Results indicate that controlling material draw-in by constraining the blank in-plane around the perimeter is an effective way of homogenising the global shear angle distribution and minimising the local maximum value. The peak shear angle was reduced from 48.2° to 37.2° following the two-stage optimisation process and in general, strains along the two principal fibre directions were also reduced during the optimisation, resulting in the reduction of potential regions of severe wrinkling.

However, whilst spring-loaded clamps can effectively control material draw-in and reduce local shear angles to an acceptable level, the peak compressive strains were found to be higher than when using a segmented blank holder constraint. Adopting blank holders can therefore help to reduce the occurrence of wrinkles (2.2 % wrinkling strain compared with 3.6 %) due to the normal force applied.

(a) Spring-loaded clamps

(b) Segmented blank-holder

Figure 7: Evolution of wrinkling strain distribution along two principal fibre directions.

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